

MICROWAVE HEATING OF THICK-SECTION
GRAPHITE FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES
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ABSTRACT

The heating characteristics of a fully cured crossply thick-section graphite fiber/epoxy composite were studied in a 2.45 Ghz resonant microwave applicator. Several temperature measurements were made at various locations on the outer surface and in the midplane of the composite during heating. The heating characteristics of the composite varied with the resonant electromagnetic mode and the fiber orientation. It was possible to maintain uniform planar temperatures and to control the temperature in the midplane at values greater than that at the surface. Higher midplane temperatures indicated that a substantial amount of microwave power was dissipated at the center region of the thick-section graphite fiber/epoxy composite. This study shows that it is feasible to process thick-section, conducting fiber reinforced composites using controlled microwave heating. In addition, the fracture surfaces of microwave and thermally cured composites were examined with a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). SEM photographs revealed that the microwave processed composites failed in a matrix failure mode while the thermally processed samples failed in a combination of interfacial and matrix failure modes. This study shows that the graphite fiber/epoxy bonding was greater in the microwave processed composites than in the thermally processed samples.

KEYWORDS: Microwave Heating; Graphite Fiber/Epoxy; Thick-section Composites; Fiber/Matrix Bonding; Failure mode.

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous graphite fiber/epoxy composites are widely used in various engineering applications due to their high mechanical performance and light weight. This type of composite is usually processed in a thermal autoclave. A temperature gradient within the composite is the major drawback in thermal processing and is due to the thermal heating mechanism, the exothermic crosslinking reaction, and the uncontrollability of the heat source. In processing thin-section composites, the temperature gradient can be eliminated by the introduction of a longer cure cycle. This gradient is, however, harder to control in thick-

section composite processing. In order to shorten the cure cycle and control the temperature gradient in the processing of thick-section samples, microwave processing techniques have been studied^{1,2,3,4,5} for this type of composite. Because of its unique heating mechanism, microwave processing offers several advantages over thermal processing of graphite fiber/epoxy composites. These advantages are controllability, fast volume heating, selective heating, and better crosslinking morphology. The controllability can be used to control or eliminate the interior thermal gradient caused by the exothermic crosslinking reaction in thin as well as thick-section composites. Fast volume heating brings the epoxy resin up to the cure temperature uniformly in a short time. Selective heating allows the graphite fiber to be heated preferentially which enhances fiber/matrix bonding⁶.

In the study of microwave curing of epoxy resins, faster reaction rates and higher ultimate extents of cure were observed as compared to those of thermal curing at the same cure temperature^{7,8,9,10}. Higher glass transition temperatures of microwave cured resins were observed as compared to those of thermally cured samples at the same extent of cure⁷. The higher T_g may be due to an orderly crosslinked network structure resulting from microwave heating. In the study of microwave processing of graphite fiber/epoxy composites, three types of microwave applicators, namely multimode microwave ovens⁵, wave guides⁴, and tunable resonant cavities^{1,2,3}, were investigated. Only the tunable resonant cavity was found to be successful in processing crossply and thick (up to 72 ply) graphite fiber/epoxy composites with uniform temperature profiles and acceptable mechanical properties¹. Only those samples which were uniformly heated in the microwave applicator were observed to have good mechanical properties. An experimental procedure for the microwave processing of 24- and 72- ply unidirectional and crossply composites with high mechanical properties has been presented earlier¹.

In the microwave processing of composites, the heating characteristics are a strong function of the electromagnetic field pattern inside the sample. For a given composite size and microwave input power of a given frequency, the electromagnetic (EM) field pattern depends on the cavity length, coupling probe length, fiber orientation, and sample location. As graphite fibers are good conductors and graphite fiber reinforced composites are high loss anisotropic materials, the electric field pattern and strength distribution in a loaded cavity are highly perturbed from those of an empty cavity. No corresponding theoretical calculations of the EM field for the cavity loaded with such complex materials have been made. The key objective in the microwave processing of graphite fiber/epoxy composite is, therefore, to experimentally find a proper cavity length, coupling probe length, composite location, and fiber orientation such that a uniform or controlled heating pattern will result inside the composite with all of the input power focused on the composite. The microwave heating characteristics of a fully cured, thick-section, crossply graphite fiber/epoxy composite were investigated using a 2.45 GHz microwave applicator to serve as a guide for the microwave processing of such composites.

Since the mechanical properties of composites are greatly effected by fiber/matrix bonding, the microwave heating effects

on this bonding were also studied. Due to the difficulty in providing a fracture surface in a thick-section composite, a 24-ply unidirectional sample was processed for fracture analysis. The delaminated surfaces of both microwave and thermally processed unidirectional composites were analyzed.

2. EXPERIMENTS

Microwave heating experiments were performed on a 7.6x7.6 x3.8cm thick-section crossply fully thermally cured graphite fiber/epoxy composite (Hercules AS4/3501-6) in a 2.45 GHz microwave applicator. A teflon disc, 10.2cm in diameter and 3.8cm thick, was placed on the top and bottom of the sample. The composite panel was placed at the center of the bottom plate in a 17.8cm tunable resonant cavity. A series of runs were conducted with fiber orientations of 0, 15, 45, 75, and 90 degrees with respect to the coupling probe using the top fiber direction as a reference for clockwise rotation. The 2.45 GHz microwave applicator and accompanying diagnostic and control system have been described elsewhere¹. Eight temperature measurements, four on the surface and four in corresponding locations in the midplane, were made using 2 fluoro optic temperature sensing systems (Luxtron 750 and Luxtron 755). One temperature was measured in the center and the others were measured at locations evenly spaced along the edges for both the surface and the midplane. Five resonant heating modes were found for each fiber orientation and each mode was used to heat the sample using a constant input power of 60W. The selection and maintenance of resonant modes has been described earlier¹. The heating was terminated when one temperature, either on the surface or in the midplane, reached 160°C.

In order to examine the bonding between fiber and matrix in microwave processed composites, a 7.6x7.6cm 24-ply unidirectional AS4/3501-6 composite was processed in the same cavity. The fabrication and processing procedures for such samples have been described elsewhere². For comparison, a 7.6x7.6cm unidirectional sample was also processed in the autoclave using the manufacturer's cure cycle. The thickness of the microwave and thermally processed composites were 4.06mm and 3.05mm, respectively. Delaminated surfaces of each sample were obtained by using a short-beam interlaminar shear test (ASTM D2344-84). The samples were subjected to 3-point bending until delamination occurred. A small amount (10-20 mg) of each coupon was removed from the delamination surface and tested for extent of cure in a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DuPont 9900). The delamination surface of each of these samples was analyzed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL JSM T330).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conditions and results for the microwave heating of a 3.8cm thick fully cured crossply graphite fiber/epoxy composite at five fiber orientations are summarized in Table 1. Five modes were located for each fiber orientation and are identified in Table 1. The time required for the highest temperature to reach 160° is listed in column 2. Columns 3, 4, and 5 contain the values of the maximum temperature difference at the surface, the midplane, and the entire composite at the end of the heating. The midplane temperatures were greater than the corresponding

surface temperature unless marked by ($T_s > T_m$) in column 5. The number in front of ($T_s > T_m$) corresponds to the number of locations where the temperature at the surface was greater than in the midplane. The types of resonant heating modes are ordered in the same way for the 0° , 15° , 75° and 90° fiber orientations as listed in column 1. The sequence is two uncontrolled-hybrid modes (UH), two coupled controlled-hybrid modes (CH), and a pseudo-single mode (PS). UH means that only one resonant heating mode can be located among several coalesced peaks. CH means that more than one resonant heating mode can be located among coalesced peaks and the resonant condition inside the cavity can be controlled in any one of them. The data in columns 3-5 show that the heating rates and temperature uniformity vary with fiber orientation and cavity length. The time required to reach 160°C was, however, usually about 50 minutes as indicated in column 2. The midplane temperatures were usually higher than the surface temperatures as shown in column 5. The higher midplane temperature suggests that the electric field inside the composite was as strong as or stronger than that at the surface.

To quantify the quality of each heating mode, the quality index (I) was introduced. The value of I is a relative dimensionless value calculated by:

$$I = \frac{a \Delta T_s + b \Delta T_m + c \Delta T_{tot} + d t}{10}$$

where a, b, c, d are relative weight factors. Factors a, b, and c have units of $1/^\circ\text{C}$ while d has units of $1/\text{min}$. The smaller the value of I, the higher the quality of the heating mode. In the processing of composites, the temperature uniformity, ΔT_s , ΔT_m , and ΔT_{tot} , are critical to the final mechanical properties. The time required to reach the control temperature can be reduced by increasing input power. Therefore, for the calculations of I in the column 6, the temperature differences were weighted more heavily than the processing time. Values for a, b, and c were arbitrarily set equal to 1, and d was set equal to 0.2. Figure 1 shows the quality index of each resonant heating mode versus the cavity length for various fiber orientations. The cavity length of each resonant heating mode was similar for the 0° , 15° , 75° , and 90° fiber orientations. The similarity increased with increasing cavity length. For the resonant heating mode between cavity lengths of 17cm and 18cm, the cavity length was essentially the same, i.e. 17.6cm. The quality index was, however, a strong function of fiber orientation and cavity length. As shown in Figure 1, there are 3 modes having an I value lower than 5. They are the CH mode of 75° fiber orientation at $L_c = 14.19\text{cm}$, $L_p = 16.41\text{mm}$, the PS mode of 75° fiber orientation at $L_c = 17.64\text{cm}$, $L_p = 18.09\text{mm}$, and the CH mode of 15° fiber orientation at $L_c = 13.89\text{cm}$, $L_p = 18.48\text{mm}$. Figure 2 shows the temperature/position/time profiles for these three modes. The temperature differences in these modes were the smallest, i.e. the planar temperature differences were between 4°C and 15°C as listed in column 3, 4, and 5 of Table 1. In the CH mode at a fiber orientation of 75° , the heating rate in the midplane was the same as that at the surface. The surface temperatures were higher than corresponding midplane temperatures at two locations, and vice versa at the other two locations as shown in Figure 2(a). In the PS mode at a fiber orientation of 75° , the heating rates of three locations were slightly higher in the midplane than at the surface while the other one was significantly higher as shown in Figure 2(b). In

the CH mode at a fiber orientation of 15° , the heating rates at all locations were higher in the midplane than at the surface as shown in Figure 2(c). These results demonstrate that a 3.8cm thick crossply fully cured graphite fiber/epoxy composite can be uniformly heated by microwave radiation with the proper selection of mode and fiber orientation. The heating rates through the thickness of a thick-section composite can also be controlled by choosing a proper mode and fiber orientation. It is, therefore, feasible to process thick-section conducting fiber reinforced composites using microwave radiation. Of the three uniform heating modes, the CH mode at a fiber orientation of 75° was the best. The quality index value of this mode was also the lowest, $I=4.4$. This suggests that I is a useful quality measure for a resonant mode.

Figure 3 shows the SEM photographs of the delaminated surfaces from the short-beam test of both the microwave and thermal samples. Both samples were fully cured as determined by DSC. For the thermally processed composite, the crack propagated only along the fiber direction as shown in Figure 3(a). The presence of matrix debris indicates, however, that the sample failed in a combination of interfacial and matrix failure modes. For the microwave processed sample, the crack propagated parallel as well as perpendicular to the fiber direction as shown in Figure 3(b). A close examination of the failed fibers revealed that the fibers were coated with a layer of epoxy as shown in Figure 3(c). This indicates that the microwave processed composite failed in the matrix failure mode. These results agree with previous findings⁶ on microwave heating of single fiber/epoxy samples which showed greater graphite fiber/epoxy bonding in microwave processing than in thermal processing.

4. CONCLUSION

Microwave heating experiments of a 3.8cm thick-section fully cured graphite fiber/epoxy composite were conducted in a 17.8cm cylindrical tunable resonant cavity using 2.45 GHz microwave radiation at fiber orientations of 0° , 15° , 45° , 75° , and 90° . Five resonant heating modes were found for each fiber orientation. The heating rate and the temperature uniformity were strong functions of the fiber orientation and the resonant heating mode. Uniform heating of the composite was achieved in the CH mode with a 75° fiber orientation at $L_c = 14.19\text{cm}$, $L_p = 16.41\text{mm}$, the PS mode at a 75° fiber orientation with $L_c = 17.64\text{cm}$, and $L_p = 18.09\text{mm}$, and the CH mode with a 15° fiber orientation at $L_c = 13.89\text{cm}$, $L_p = 18.48\text{mm}$. For the CH mode in the 75° fiber orientation, the heating rate in the midplane was the same as that at the surface. For the PS mode in the 75° fiber orientation and the CH mode in the 15° fiber orientation, the heating rate in the midplane was higher than that at the surface. The results of this study indicate that it is feasible to process graphite fiber or other conductor reinforced thick-section composites using microwave radiation.

The SEM fracture analysis of the delaminated surface showed that the microwave processed composite failed in a matrix failure mode while the thermally processed sample failed in a combination of matrix and interfacial failure modes during short-beam shear test. This result indicates that the fiber/epoxy bonding in the microwave processed AS4/3501-6 composite was stronger than that in the thermally processed sample.

6. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Conditions and Results for Microwave Heating of 3.8cm Thick Fully Cured Crossply AS4/3501-6 Composite.

Table 1.1 0° Fiber Orientation

Mode Type & Lc(cm) Lp(mm)	Time* to reach 160 °C (min.)	ΔT_s (°C)	ΔT_m (°C)	Overall ΔT_{tot} (°C)	Quality Index
UH Lc=10.94 Lp=16.30	42-M	21	22	30	8.1
UH Lc=12.20 Lp=18.87	60-M	15	17	30	7.6
CH Lc=13.91 Lp=17.02	44-M	17	14	25	6.5
CH Lc=14.38 Lp= 9.69	51-M	10	16	15 2(Ts>Ti)	5.1
PS Lc=17.65 Lp=18.37	46-M	13	15	22	5.9

* M or S indicate that the location for the temperature probe which reached 160°C was at midplane or surface.

Table 1.2 15° Fiber Orientation

Mode Type & Lc(cm) Lp(mm)	Time* to reach 160 °C (min.)	ΔT_g (°C)	ΔT_m (°C)	Overall ΔT_{tot} (°C)	Quality Index
UH Lc=11.68 Lp=21.89	42-S	18	20	30 3(Ts>Ti)	7.6
UH Lc=12.31 Lp=17.19	49-M	6	16	22	5.4
CH Lc=13.89 Lp=18.48	49-M	5	10	23	4.8
CH Lc=14.25 Lp=15.45	47-M	8	19	19	5.5
PS Lc=17.79 Lp=17.01	39-M	8	18	25	5.9

Table 1.3 45° Fiber Orientation.

Mode Type & Lc(cm) Lp(mm)	Time* to reach 160 °C (min.)	ΔT_g (°C)	ΔT_m (°C)	Overall ΔT_{tot} (°C)	Quality Index
PS Lc=10.71 Lp=13.36	55-S	10	12	20 3(Ts>Ti)	5.3
CH Lc=11.52 Lp=14.55	39-S	30	12	45 4(Ts>Ti)	9.5
CH Lc=12.56 Lp=21.46	37-S	43	16	43 2(Ts>Ti)	10.9
UH Lc=14.04 Lp=13.73	54-M	13	10	30	6.6
PS Lc=17.64 Lp=20.05	29-M	26	48	65	14.5

Table 1.4 75° Fiber Orientation

Mode Type & Lc(cm) Lp(mm)	Time* to reach 160 °C (min.)	ΔT_g (°C)	ΔT_m (°C)	Overall ΔT_{tot} (°C)	Quality Index
UH Lc=11.36 Lp=18.85	40-S	30	4	32 4(Ts>Ti)	7.4
UH Lc=12.29 Lp=17.09	44-M	10	19	38	7.5
CH Lc=14.04 Lp=12.02	44-M	21	23	35	8.8
CH Lc=14.19 Lp=16.41	52-S	15	6	13 2(Ts>Ti)	4.4
PS Lc=17.64 Lp=18.09	55-M	13	4	20	4.8

Table 1.5 90° Fiber Orientation

Mode Type & Lc(cm) Lp(mm)	Time* to reach 160 °C (min.)	ΔT_g (°C)	ΔT_m (°C)	Overall ΔT_{tot} (°C)	Quality Index
UH Lc=11.07 Lp=19.37	23-M	43	53	88	18.9
UH Lc=12.45 Lp=17.37	49-M	15	17	39	8.1
CH Lc=13.86 Lp=14.47	39-M	35	25	50	8.8
CH Lc=14.32 Lp=20.89	40-M	15	26	35	8.4
PS Lc=17.64 Lp=17.72	34-M	22	29	51	10.9

FIGURE 1. Quality Index versus cavity length for each fiber orientation.

2(a). A CH mode at 75° fiber orientation.

2(b). A PS mode at 75° fiber orientation.

2(c). A CH mode at 15° fiber orientation.

FIGURE 2. Temperature/position/time profiles for three resonant heating modes having index value lower than 5.

3(a). Thermal sample

3(b). Microwave sample

3(c). Microwave processed composite

FIGURE 3. SEM photograph of the delaminated surface for microwave and thermally processed AS4/3501-6 composites.